

Explain different search mechanisms with practical examples.

Based on theories and methods/tools present in other disciplines, a number of models have been created in order to discover satisfactory solutions for information retrieval problems.

1. Boolean retrieval models

1.1 Standard Boolean

Boolean logic allows a user to logically relate multiple concepts together to define what information is needed. Typically, the Boolean functions apply to processing tokens identified anywhere within an item. The typical Boolean operators are AND, OR, and NOT. These operations are implemented utilizing set intersection, set union and set difference methods. A couple of frameworks presented the concept of 'Exclusive OR' but it is identical to a somewhat more complex query utilizing the other operators and isn't generally valuable to clients since most clients don't get it. The typical Boolean operations deliver the following results:

"A AND B" retrieves those things that contain both terms A and B.

"A OR B" retrieves those things that contain the term A or the term B or both.

"A NOT B" retrieves those things that contain term A and not contain term B.

1.2 Weighted Boolean

The two major approaches to producing queries are Boolean and natural language. Natural language queries are effortlessly represented within statistical model. Issues emerge when Boolean queries are related with weighted index systems. A few of the issues are related with how the logic (AND, OR, NOT) operators work with weighted values and how weights are related with the query terms. If the operators are deciphered in their nominal translation, they act too restrictive or as well general. The objective is to perform the normal Boolean operations and after that refine the results utilizing weighting strategies. The query process uses the weights in conjunction with any weights allotted to terms in the query to decide a scalar value (rank value) utilized in foreseeing the probability that an item fulfills the query. The results are displayed to the client in order of the rank value from highest number to lowest number.

Example - For example, if we want to search for an article about the Benefits of Yoga, we also require information about Simple Yoga Poses. The Boolean operator AND will narrow the search by including all the content or articles related to both yoga poses and the benefits of yoga. AND operator helps to connect various information and search the actual required content we are looking for. OR operator is used to choosing between 2 topics. Using the NOT operator, we can negotiate the content we do not require.

2. Fuzzy logic model

Fuzzy logic supports values - true and false as well as other values in between. The conceptual fuzzy logic was presented by Professor Lotfi A. Zadeh. The fundamental objective of the fuzzy logic is to create a model that may be near to natural language process. It is a fitting device for modeling the kind of instability related with vagueness with imprecision. Fuzzy retrieval gives the capability to find spellings of words that are similar to the entered search term. This function is essentially utilized to compensate for mistakes in spelling of words. Fuzzy retrieval increases recall at the cost of decreasing precision. In the process of extending a query term, fuzzy retrieval incorporates other terms that have similar spellings; giving more weight to words in the database that have similar word lengths and position of the characters as the entered term. A fuzzy search on the term 'computer' would consequently incorporate the following words from the information database: 'computer', 'compiter', 'computer', 'compute'. An additional enhancement may look up the proposed elective spelling and if it is a valid word with a different meaning, incorporate it in the search with a low ranking or not incorporate it at all (e.g., 'commuter'). Systems permit the specification of the greatest number of few terms that the expansion incorporates within the query. Fuzzy retrieval has its maximum usage in a framework that accepts items that have been optical character recognised. In the OCR process, a hardcopy item is scanned into a binary image. The OCR process is a pattern recognition process that segments the scanned in image into important sub-regions, considering a segment - the zone defining a single character. The OCR process will at that point decide the character and interpret into an internal computer encoding. Based upon the original quality of the hardcopy this process presents mistakes in perceiving characters. With conventional quality input, systems achieve in the 90-99 percent range of exactness. Since these are character errors all through the content, fuzzy retrieval permits location of items of interest compensating for the incorrect characters.

Example- One of the most famous applications of fuzzy logic is that of the Sendai Subway system in Sendai, Japan. This control of the Nanboku line, developed by Hitachi, used a fuzzy controller to run the train all day long. This made the line one of the smoothest running subway systems in the world and increased efficiency as well as stopping time. This is also an example of the earlier acceptance of fuzzy logic in the east since the subway went into operation in 1988.

3. Probabilistic retrieval model

In addition to a vector space model, the other prominent approach is probabilistic retrieval model. The model has been most successful in this area is the Bayesian approach. This approach is natural to information systems and depends upon the theories of evidential reasoning (drawing conclusions from evidence). The Bayesian approach could be applied as part of index term weighting, but naturally is applied as part of the retrieval process by calculating the relationship between an item and a specific query. The probabilistic approach is based upon the application of the theory of probability in information retrieval systems. Van Rijsbergen proposed that a measure of

the probability of relevance of a given document to a particular theory be based on a Vector representing that document. He postulated that the pattern of index terms in relevant documents will differ from their pattern in non-relevant documents. Probability approach will help to analyze term-clustering, frequency weighting, relevance weighting and ranking. The probabilistic approach of a retrieval model is based on the assumption that the distribution of the indexing features tells us about the relevance of a document. This approach adopts a retrieval model which optimizes the retrieval effectiveness according to the Probability Ranking Principle (PRP). In this method the system replies to a query by providing the beginning of a list of documents that are ranked in descending order of scores that either represent probabilities themselves or could be mapped to probabilities by means of an order preserving transformation. These scores often called Retrieval Status Values (RSV) which are dependent on document descriptions consisting of appropriate statistical information about the indexing features. Such score may also depend on domain dependent parameters that are estimated by means of additional data e.g. by a thesaurus.

4. Vector space model

The Vector Space Model steps can be divided into three stages. The first stage is the document indexing where the subject bearing terms are extracted from the document text. Many of the words in a document do not describe the content, like, the, is, are, in, to, of, etc. These are called non-significant words or stop words. In case of automatic indexing, these terms are removed from the document vector, so the document will only be represented by the subject representing terms. The second stage is the weighting of the indexed terms to enhance the retrieval of document relevant to the user. The last stage ranks the document with respect to the query according to users search interest. It is a retrieval model which constitutes a fairly large class of retrieval methods, each consisting of an indexing method and a retrieval function. The indexing method generates description vectors, and the retrieval function generates retrieval status values by comparing the query description vector with the document description vectors. Application- Vectors space models can have many applications, such as: Information Extraction — to answer questions in the style of who, what, where, how, etc, Machine Translation & Chatbots Programing.

4. Linguistic model

Linguistic model for information retrieval studies the information retrieval from the perspective of the properties of language. Information retrieval is provided by features of natural language as well as artificial language. The languages do three types of functions:

- i) They represent the subject of documents;
- ii) The information problem of users is represented in terms of language;
- iii) Language is used in computer processing and in searching and retrieving information.

The language works on three bases:

- a) Semantic basis which conveys meaning from one human being to another;
- b) The syntactic basis which helps formation of semantics in the use of grammar;
- c) The vocabulary, which gives different meanings to terms for formation of sentences, paragraphs and other structures. Application of transformational grammar as well as parsing techniques provide processing speed of the language for information retrieval. Also, indexing language with control provides a basic model for information retrieval. Use of associative mathematics in search logic and in search expression formulation, provide another type of language control in information retrieval. This linguistic model forms an essential base for information retrieval.

References

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